

Number of States E power (degrees of freedom) from Conservation of Energy?

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In the literature (1), one often sees the expression: number of states $G(E)$ proportional to E^f , where E is the total energy and f the number of degrees of freedom. From this result, one may obtain the Maxwell-Boltzmann factor by considering $G(E-e)$ where G = the number of states, i.e. a power expansion is performed and $G(E-e)$ divided by $G(E)$ proportional to E^f as performed in (1).

We argue that using $G(E-e_1)$, $G(E-e_2)$ and $G(E-e_1-e_2)$ should lead to probabilities which respect conservation of energy, i.e. $p(e_1)p(e_2) = p(e_1+e_2)$. One does not need to know the form of G in this case and can immediately obtain $p(e_i) = C \exp(-e_i/T)$. We argue, however, that given $p(e_1)p(e_2)=p(e_1+e_2)$, one may find that $G(E)$ proportional to E^f is a simple solution. We also show that one must be careful in taking a power series because even though $e \ll E$, that does not mean one may necessarily retain only the first power of e in a Taylor series. In the case of $G(E)$ proportional to E^f , both the first power e expansion and higher power expansion respect conservation of energy $p(e_1)p(e_2)=p(e_1+e_2)$ and thus necessarily lead to the Maxwell-Boltzmann factor

Number of States Proportional to E^f

In the literature (1), one often sees the statement:

number of states $G(E)$ proportional to E^f ((1))

where E is total energy and f , the number of degrees of freedom (linked to energy we argue).

From this statement, one may use:

$$p(e_i) = G(E-e_i) / G(E) \quad ((2))$$

Using ((1)), one obtains an explicit result for ((2)) (namely the Maxwell-Boltzmann factor), but we suggest that one does not need to know the form ((1)).

Conservation of Energy

We suggest that one may consider: $G(E-e_1)$, $G(E-e_2)$ and $G(E-e_1-e_2)$. We argue that e_1+e_2 is a certain amount of energy which is removed from the system (as well as two particles) and that one can remove any $e_i+e_j=e_1+e_2$ and have the same $G(E-e_1-e_2)$. In other words, this is an energy distribution problem.

Next, consider the possibility of expanding $G(E-e_1-e_2)$ and retaining only the first order term in e_1+e_2 . This is not always possible in general, but we assume the special case here.

$$G(E-e_1-e_2) = G(E) - (e_1+e_2) dG/dE + \dots \quad ((3))$$

In such a case: $G(E-e_1-e_2)/G(E) = 1 - (e_1+e_2) d \ln G/dE + \dots$ ((4))

We caution that ((4)) is not always possible, i.e one cannot only retain the linear term in all cases as we later show. If ((4)) is true, then:

$p(e_1+e_2)$ proportional to $\exp(-e_1/T) \exp(-e_2/T)$ ((5)) where $1/T$ is $d \ln G/dE$.

Using the same first term in e expansion for $G(E-e_1)$ and $G(E-e_2)$ yields:

$p(e_1)$ proportional to $\exp(-e_1/T)$ and $p(e_2)$ proportional to $\exp(-e_2/T)$ ((5))

Thus, under the assumption of a linear expansion: $p(e_1)p(e_2) = p(e_1+e_2)$ which demonstrates conservation of energy.

We next ask: Under the assumption of a valid linear expansion in e , can one find an explicit form for $G(E)$?

We argue that $G(E) = E^{\text{power } f}$, where f is the number of degrees of freedom ((6)) suffices.

For N particles with only kinetic energy, $f=3N$. It is not, however, always the case that a linear expansion in e is sufficient. For example:

$$\begin{aligned} G(E-e)/G(E) &= (E-e)^{\text{power } f} / G(E) = E^{-e/3N} (E)^{\text{power } 3N-1} / G(E) \\ &= 1 - 3Ne/E \quad ((7)) \end{aligned}$$

It is very possible that $3Ne > E$ in which case the first order term is not sufficient. It is only fine if $3Ne/E \ll 1$.

In the case that $3Ne/E > 1$, one needs to retain more terms in the power expansion which is not a problem. For the special case of ((6)):

$$G(E-e) / G(E) = 1 - 3Ne/E + \frac{1}{2} 3N(3N-1) ee / EE + \frac{1}{3!} 3N(3N-1)(3N-2) eee / EEE + \dots \quad ((8))$$

One may see that if $3N-1 \approx 3N$, that one obtains an exponential expansion of $\exp(-e/(E/3N))$ even in the case of $3Ne/E > 1$. Thus, in both the linear case and the expansion of multiple e powers one has the $\exp(-e/T)$ form which is linked with conservation of energy if one uses $G(E) = E^{\text{power } f}$.

Conclusion

In conclusion, in the literature (1) one often sees a priori the statement $G(E) = \text{number of states} = E^f$, where E is total energy and f degrees of freedom (linked to energy we argue). From this, one may derive the Maxwell-Boltzmann factor. We suggest instead to use conservation of energy. We argue that if one may expand $G(E-e_1-e_2)$ in terms of e_1+e_2 and retain only the linear term, then dividing by $G(E)$ yields $p(e_1+e_2) = p(e_1)p(e_2) = \exp(-e_1/T) \exp(-e_2/T)$. (We also perform the expansion of $G(E-e_1)$ and $G(E-e_2)$. A solution for $G(E)$ in this case which is compatible with the conservation of energy result is: $G(E)$ proportional to E^f ((9))

It is not always sufficient to retain only the first order e_1+e_2 in an expansion. One must thus consider the case of ((9)) when many e powers are required. We show above that even in this case, one obtains $p(e) = C \exp(-e/T)$ so $\exp(-e/T)$ holds still as does conservation of energy: $p(e_1)p(e_2) = p(e_1+e_2)$.

References

1. Reif, F. Fundamentals of Statistical and Thermal Physics (McGraw Hill 1965) P62, p 108